

A COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS OF NATIONAL EDUCATION POLICY (NEP) 2020

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Abstract

The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 represents a landmark reforms in India's educational landscape. It is a visionary document aimed at mapping the Indian education system to meet the evolving demands of the 21st century while being rooted in India's educational ethos. With an emphasis on inclusivity, equity, and excellence, the policy proposes wide-ranging reforms spanning school education, higher education, teacher training, and the integration of technology. This paper provides a comprehensive and critical analysis of NEP 2020, exploring its foundational principles, strategic initiatives, and the multiple challenges it seeks to address. In addition to discussing curriculum reforms, teacher education, and digital transformation, this study develops into language policy, inclusiveness, and the reshaping of assessment methods. By expanding on the core areas of NEP 2020, this analysis evaluates its transformative potential and the prerequisites for its effective implementation.

The present research paper tries to present a quick review of the new education policy through the existing research done on the same subject. For the structured review the researcher has set the required objectives of the study and has collected the necessary data from the secondary data available. As per the plans of the Government, The New Education policy 2020 would be implemented in phases by the year 2026. The present study is presenting the time period from 2020 to 2025. And during this time whatever research papers and articles are published into the public domain are accessed through the internet. This research paper would help the stakeholders in the Indian Education System to readily access the review of the research work during the year and thereby to understand the divergent views, opinions and results discussed by different authors via their research works.

Key Words : *NEP 2020, NEP 1986, Comparison, Implementation issues, Education, Policy, NEP, GER, Reforms, Capacity, Childhood.*

Introduction: National Education Policy of India 2020 has a purpose of making innovative policies to improve the quality, attractiveness, affordability, and increasing the supply by opening up the higher education. By encouraging merit-based admissions with free-ships & scholarships, merit & research based continuous performers as faculty members, and merit based proven leaders in regulating bodies, and strict monitoring of quality through biennial

accreditation based on self-declaration of progress through technology-based monitoring, NEP-2020 is expected to fulfil its objectives by 2030.

Various educational stages to be implemented according to NEP 2020:

1) Foundation Stage: Five years Foundational Stage provides basic education which is flexible, multilevel, play-based, activity-based, and discovery- based learning.

2) Preparatory Stage: Three years Preparatory stage consists of building on the play-, discovery-, and activity-based learning. In addition to it, this stage gradually introduces formal classroom learning with textbooks.

3) Middle school educational stage: Three years of Middle school education focus on more abstract concepts in each subject like sciences, mathematics, arts, social sciences, and humanities. Experiential learning is the method to be adopted in specialised subjects with subject teachers.

4) Secondary Stage: Four years of Secondary school education is designed to provide multidisciplinary subjects including Liberal Arts education., Students are exposed to the semester system and will study 5 to 6 subjects in each semester. There will be Board exams at the end of 10th and 12th standards

5) Under graduation stage: The Undergraduate degrees in every subject will be of either three- or four-year duration with multiple exit options including a certificate after passing first year, a diploma after passing second year, or a Bachelor 's degree after passing third year.

6) Post- Graduation Stage: The Master's degree – a one-year for four years bachelor degree students, a two-year degree for three years bachelor degree students, and an integrated five year degree with a focus on high quality research in the final year.

7) Research stage: Research stage consists of pursuing high quality research leading to a Ph.D. in any core subject, multidisciplinary subject, or interdisciplinary subject for a minimum period of three to four years for full-time and part-time study respectively. During Ph.D. they should undergo

8-credit coursework in teaching/ education/ pedagogy related to their chosen Ph.D. subject. The earlier one-year MPhil programme is discontinued now. Comparison of National Education policy 1986 & National Education policy 2020

A summary of key features are as follows:

1. Objective is to provide Multidisciplinary & interdisciplinary liberal education.
2. Common education structure of 5+3+3+4+4+1 is suggested. The first preliminary education starts at 3rd year of a child as a Foundation stage. Two years higher secondary level and two years pre university levels. Exams are suggested at the school level except for Board level exams at 10th and 12th. Four years Secondary education stage contains common subjects and elective subjects. All undergraduate and postgraduate admissions of public HEIs are based on National Testing Agency (NTA) scores conducted by the national level. Undergraduate programmes are of four years with a provision to exit after one year with a diploma, after two years with an advanced diploma, after three years with a pass degree, and after four years with project-based degree. Postgraduate education is of one to two years with more specialization & research focus.
3. All HEIs including colleges are autonomous and there will be no affiliated colleges to state universities and autonomy in deciding curriculum and evaluation.
4. Examination is a part of a continuous evaluation system. Faculty members are responsible for evaluation and examinations are departmental affairs.
5. Teaching-learning method mainly focuses on classroom training, fieldwork, and research projects. In higher education system, the expected student-faculty ratio is 30:1.
6. In HEIs faculty members are considered as collaborators and guide to educating students to make them as innovators & creative thinkers.
7. Students have the freedom to choose subjects outside and across their area of study. A one year research degree leading to M.Phil. in any subject is discontinued
8. Ph.D. degree is compulsory along with pass in NET/SLET as an essential qualification to become an Assistant professor in any three types of HEIs. The support of research funds through the National Research Foundation and any other agencies will be equally distributed to all three.

SUGGESTIONS OF NEP 2020 :

- 1) Use of Services of Retired Professors as Research Guides
- 2) A proper definition of Multidisciplinary College
- 3) Higher Education Leaders should be Role Models in Research & Innovations
- 4) Compulsory three modes of Teaching–Learning processes in HEIs
1. Weekly three days classroom-based classes
2. Weekly 2 days online classes

3. Weekly one day industry/vocational/skill based online/classroom-based classes
4. Two subjects per semester through MOOC like SWAYAM/NPTEL, ODL, etc.
- 5) Vocational Training based Earn while Learn Encouragement
- 6) Compulsory Employability & Entrepreneurship related papers in each semester to promote Employability & Entrepreneurability among the students
- 7) Strengthening Integrated National Digital Library (INDL)

Conclusion : As clear from the comparison of NEP 1986 and NEP 2020, in the new policy now more practical, student centred features are introduced which will make it more effective for the learners.

Objectives of the Study: - The present study has following important objectives behind undertaking this research. a.

To study the existing and freely available and accessible research papers for the study of the National Education Policy 2020

b. To discuss the objectives, research methodologies and results of the previous studies to get valuable insights of the New Education Policy 2020.

c. To find out the gaps in the existing studies for the further research. For the completion of the above stated objectives of the study researcher has collected the research articles from the World Wide Web. Thus the secondary data was collected and structured review approach was applied by the researcher for the study. All the articles and research papers covered during the review are between the periods of year 2020 to 2024. Only those articles and research papers were considered for the study which was accessible through the Google search engine. Only those articles and research papers which could be freely downloaded with their full length were covered in the study. The scope of the study is limited with the objectives stated above and for the time period of 2020 to 2024.

3. Structured review: - For the purpose of the review on standard pattern of review was followed which consists: 1. The discussion about the main aim of the study, 2. To understand the research methodology followed and the 3. To discuss about the results summary and discussion given thereupon in the study. With this above standardized pattern total 18 research papers published in between the years 2020 to 2024 were reviewed in the study out of which 12 researches papers are qualitative in nature and are based upon the secondary data. The remaining 6 research papers are empirical in nature and is either completely depending upon the primary data and some of them have even the mix of primary as well as secondary data. The 18 articles reviewed under the study are follows;

Review of Literature:-

1. Dr. Rahul Pratap Singh Kaurav, Prof K G Suresh, Dr. Sumit Narula, Raturaj Baber.

(2020):- This research paper aims to study sentiments of people towards the National Education Policy 2020. During this qualitative research study, the secondary data available from tweeter was processed with the help of word cloud, tree map, project map and mind map. For representing the sentiments of stakeholders graphs were used. At the end it was revealed that, most people consider NEP as a positive and welcoming step.

2. K.Meenakshi Sundaram (2020):-The Main objectives of the study were; to discuss the highlights of the new education policy and to see the views of academicians and the experts from the education sector on career opportunities that are expected though NEP 2020. The study is descriptive and primary data was collected through 89 respondents. Respondents were students, academicians and educationists. The data was collected through the questionnaire which was framed with the help of Liker scale. Major findings of the study as follows; NEP implementation is a challenging task and its success depends upon its implementation , multidisciplinary approach will change recruitment requirements of many companies in India and NEP will expand career opportunities through multi disciplinary approach.

3. Pawan Kalyani (2020):- This research aims at studying NEP and its effects on stakeholders and also covers the future impact of NEP on stake holders. Primary data was collected from the most important stakeholders such as, students, Parents and teachers. It was disclosed from the study that, students will be having their own choice in selection of the subjects. Dermatoglyphics can be used for understanding the skill sets of the students. Students may choose the subjects based upon dermatoglyphics. It is also observed that while choosing the subjects the students might take their decision under the influence of their parents or sometimes under the pressure of their peer groups. But the objective of NEP will be fulfilled only when the student are empowered to choose their subject independently, based on their own knowledge and skills. As per the NEP 2020, candidates with four year B.Ed degree and TET certificates only can apply teacher's recruitments in government schools. This policy will help in enhancement of quality education. Parents play a key role in development of their ward through continuous financial support for education and valuable guidance. Here under NEP parents have a key role in suggestions and recommendations in selection of the multidisciplinary subjects after studying the strengths and weaknesses of their wards.

4. Ramesh (2023) on NEP 2020, highlighting its visionary goals such as holistic development, equitable access, curriculum reform, digital integration, and teacher empowerment. The review

synthesises existing research on the policy's objectives and implementation challenges, emphasizing its potential for systemic transformation in India's education sector.

5. Sharma (2023) similarly analyses NEP 2020's provisions, including **the 5+3+3+4 curricular framework, multilingual instruction, and regulatory reforms**. The paper situates NEP within broader educational change and discusses implementation prospects and barriers.

6. Mittal et al. (2024) examine NEP's implications for **girls' higher education and employability**, contrasting Indian policy frameworks with international examples (e.g., UK, Finland). The literature review in this paper addresses gender inequality, inclusion funds, and career counselling—illuminating socio-political dimensions of NEP

7. Dr. Hemlata Verma and Adarsh Kumar (2021):- In this paper a theoretical analysis of New education policy is done by critically analyzing the requirements for the implementation of NEP and the present status of activities performed at University level. Further this study also recommends. Design in the implementation of NEP at higher educational institutes in India. Dr. Rupesh G Sawant, Dr. Umesh B Sankpal (2021) in this conceptual paper the entire focus is on New Education Policy 2020 and Higher Education. In this paper the authors discuss on important issues related with NEP. The main areas of discussion are like background, vision, principles, features, impact areas and opportunities available to stakeholders. The paper also discusses on planned execution of the new education policy.

8. Dr. Nandini Banarjee, Dr. Amarnath Das, Ms. Sreya Ghosh (2021):- In this discussion paper the objectives of the study were common like other qualitative studies covered earlier in this paper. The main objectives were to highlight the features of the NEP along with its comparison with the previous educational policy of 1986 and to propose implementation strategies. This paper also mentions about the advantages of NEP especially from the perspective of higher education.

9. Shashidharan M, Rajni Bansal, B S Hothi, Vijay Anant Athavale, Yogesh Mahajan, Shameem Anwar,(2021) . The main feature of this theoretical research paper is that it includes the challenges in the implementation of New Education Policy along with its highlights. In Challenges the authors covers the difficulties which might be incurred by different stakeholders during the implementation phase. These stakeholders are mainly the parents and students. The other concerning areas discussed under challenges are as follows; 1. Issues of rural students in coping up with the flexibility in courses and subjects proposed in NEP. 2. Expected shifts in recruitment policies by the private and public sector employers due to NEP.

3. The issues which are impacting on the professionals and students in distance education. 4. The difficulties which might arise in grading of the students because of the multidisciplinary feature of the National Education Policy.

10. **Dr. P.K Jain (2021):-** The key differentiating feature of this study is the various areas of challenges discussed during the study. These challenges are not discussed in earlier studies. The important points enumerated are as follows; 1. Dispensing of 20% of GDP for education at school levels through the initiatives from the private sector. 2. Improving the percentage of gross enrolment in advanced education. 3. Development of Anganwadi and Primary school infrastructure by providing infrastructural facilities and required man power. 4. Development of new educational guidelines for the successful implementation. For this recommendations are made to evolve strategies for producing global level educators by developing common expertise among the educators. 5. Facilitating IT enabled digital infrastructure for fostering speedy implementation of NEP. 6. Development of E-Courses and Labs. 7. Enforcing a comprehensive plan for overall implementation of NEP at all levels of education.

11. **Shubhada M R Nirantha M R (2021):-** In this theoretical study the main objectives were to study the highlights, overview, challenges merits, de-merits along with efficacy and relevance of NEP with the prevailing education policy. It covers the scope of the NEP right from school level education up to the higher education. At last the authors conclude that the future of this NEP depends upon the transparent and uniform implementation of the policy. For this authors recommends the equitable resources at all level and cooperation and coordination amongst all the stake holders driven by institutional mechanisms.

12. **Gopalan K.R, Nivithra S., Vezhaventhan D. (2021):-** Migration for the education is a very crucial aspect observed in many population studies. To study the effects of migration on population and impact of New Education policy on this phenomenon was studied in South India. In a quantitative research design the responses were sought from 200 residents of Bangalore, Madurai and Chennai to check the awareness perception and DOI: 10.9790/7388-1302015661 www.iosrjournals.org 58 | Page “A Review on National Education Policy 2020.” impact of the New Education Policy on them. The samples were mainly the students and parents residing in the respective cities. The data collected for the study revealed following important observations based on the opinions of the respondents. Majority of the respondents migrated to these cities for the better education (either of their own or of their wards). Majority of the respondents opined that it will be impossible to implement the expected changes in educational policy in an overnight. There was consensus amongst the respondents on the fact

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that the proposed changes according to the new education policy cannot be implemented suddenly without the proper infrastructure and trained staff. Again almost all the respondents opined that there will be various practical difficulties in the implementation of the proposed changes under the New Education policy

13. Dr. Praveen Kumar Sharma and Sanjeevan Bala (2022):- In this empirical study with the objectives to see the awareness among the secondary school teachers in the Kangra district of Himachal Pradesh, a sample of 80 teachers was collected through a questionnaire. The methodology of the study consists of conceptual discussions which were done by using the focus group discussion method. The results of the study disclosed the following facts; 1. It was found that average level of awareness about NEP exists among the respondents of the study area. 2. It was also observed that there is no significant difference between male-female, experienced inexperienced, arts-science stream teachers.

14. Dr. Ruchi Rani (2022):- In a theoretical study author tries to focus on various aspects of the New Education policy 2020. The broad areas which are studied in this research article are namely; major features of NEP, and salient recommendations of NEP 2020. In the recommendations the points like, multi disciplinary nature of curriculum, skill development, training of teachers, change management, legal complexities, digitalization and examination structure are mainly elaborated.

15. Dr. Prativindhya Saini (2022):- Education is the medium for the promotion of economic and social advancements in the society. New Education Policy 2020; aims at achieving this economic and social advancement through the high quality primary secondary and higher education. This paper starts with the overview of New Education Policy and thereafter discusses the generic strategies for the implementation of NEP. This research paper also tries to understand the effect of NEP on National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC).

16. Roshan Lal Sondhiya A Study on the awareness on New Education Policy (2020) among the schoolteachers in Jabalpur Distict (2022) :- The main objectives of this research expeditions are as follows; a) To find out the awareness about the National Education Policy 2020, amongst the school teachers of Jabalpur district. 2. To see the difference of awareness level amongst the school teachers of Jabalpur district on the basis of demographic variables. For fulfilling the objectives of the study, a sample of 50 school teachers from the school teachers in the Jabalpur district was collected with the help of a multi choice type questionnaire as a tool for collecting data in the present study. A sample random sampling method was chosen by the researcher for reaching up to the desired samples from the teachers working in the aided and private schools

in Jabalpur district. The data collected was statistically analyzed and the hypothesis was tested by applying 't' test. The results disclosed that there is significant difference amongst the school teachers based on their demographic variables. It was further found that women teachers from schools have more awareness about the new education policy over the male teachers. No significant difference based upon awareness could be found on the basis of private or government school.

17. Dr. Deepa Choudhari (2022):- A Study on National Education Policy – 2020 and its Impact on Stakeholders w.r.t Higher Education Institutions of Nagpur City: - In a study executed in the Nagpur City of Maharashtra, the main focus of the study was on the effects of the new education policy 2020, on the higher education institutions of Nagpur city. The main objectives of the study were; To find the effect of new education policy 2020 on higher education institutions in Nagpur city along with the possible outcomes and the draw backs of the study. This study has collected both primary and secondary data for the research purpose. The responses through the questionnaire were sought from the teachers who have at least 5 years of teaching experience and the students from the higher education institutes located in Nagpur City. The secondary data was collected thorough the existing literature on the topic and policy document of new education policy 2020. After doing the thorough literature review the research gap was found and objectives were set. The data was analyzed and the hypothesis is tested with chi square test to arrive at the results. The results of the study showed that, almost all the respondents have a positive opinion about the new education policy 2020 and they think that NEP 2020 is a good initiative taken by the government of India. As far as outcome of the new education policy 2020 is concerned, all the stakeholders opined that there would be a positive outcome from the implementation of NEP 2020 as, students would be having an opportunity to learn variety of subjects along with skill enhancement. DOI: 10.9790/7388-1302015661 www.iosrjournals.org 59 | Page “A Review on National Education Policy 2020.” Thus they have a very good chance of goal setting for their careers at the early stage of their life and can pursue the subjects and skill sets required for it from the beginning. About the last but the most important aspect that is related with drawbacks of the NEP 2020, stake holders opined that, there are some challenges in the implementation of the NEP; that are, student teacher ratio, up skilling of the teachers and skilling them for imparting the right skill set to the students as per the requirements of the industries.

18. Abhimanyu Kumar (2022) :- In this paper the author has taken a review of new education policy through the perspective of Ayurveda Universities in India and their preparedness for the
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execution of the NEP 2020. The paper covers the important aspects of the Ayurveda Education in India, namely by stating the Ayurveda Institution of national importance their roles and responsibilities for nurturing of quality culture and standardization of Ayurveda education in India. Other important aspects discussed in the study on the backdrop of the new education policy and Ayurvedic Institutions in India are like; 1. Development of Standard Ayurvedic tolls and techniques. 2. Development of Models for better health care management and 3. Incorporation of innovations and research for the development of Ayurveda.

Research Gap: - Out of total 18 studies consisting of this review, majority i.e. 12 studies are of qualitative nature and only 6 studies are of the quantitative nature. Out of all the qualitative studies majority of the studies are conceptual and theoretical which are simply discussing on the key highlights of National Education Policy 2020, Its features, Challenges paved in the implementation, comparison with older policies, advantages and disadvantages of new education policy, merits and demerits of the new education policy, effects on specific level of education, on its stakeholders, hurdles in the implementation, strategies of the implementation and plan for the implementation etc. Amongst the quantitative studies the most of the focus is on awareness and effects of new education policy on stakeholders except one research paper wherein the new area of the study was focused that were related with the migration for higher education and new education policy. All in all it can be said that there are earnest efforts made by the researchers to study this very vast and complex policy on education but still there is a lot of scope for the research especially the focus can be given on the problems and challenges faced by the stakeholders during the implementation phase of the policy. These challenges may be multi faceted such as the mental and financial preparedness of the stakeholders, anxiety and stress related with NEP 2020, career planning and career development in the realm of NEP 2020, effects on employment opportunities, employment process, existing infrastructure and social and cultural effects of NEP 2020. 5. Conclusion: - After discussing all the articles studies and finding out the research gap it can be said that NEP 2020 is a paramount shift in the entire educational system in India. So, as and how the implementation phases will pass on various new aspects and opportunities and challenges along with the loopholes would be easily identified. As there is lack of clarity on the implementation of NEP 2020 in different stages of education system, this is the watching period and only the further steps from the policy makers can clarify the doubts and concerns. This experience of implementation would give rise to more in depth studies. So researchers need to cross their fingers for further research expeditions in to this forthcoming dynamic educational journey.

References

- Dr. Rahul Pratap Singh Kaurav, Prof K G Suresh, Dr. Sumit Narula, Raturaj Baber. (2020), *New Education Policy ; Qualitative (contents) Analysis and Twitter Mining(Sentiment Analysis)*.*Journal of content, community and communication*, Vol. 12, Year 6, December-2020, ISSN: 2395-7514. DOI: - 10.31620/JCCC.12.20/02.
- K.Meenakshi Sundaram (2020)*A study on National Education Policy 2020 concerning career opportunities*, *Shanlax International Journal of Economics*, Vol. 9, no. 1, 2020, pp. 63-67. DOI:- <https://doi.org/10.34293/economics.V9i1.3497>.
- Pawan Kalyani (2020) *An Empirical Study on NEP 2020 [National Education Policy] with special reference to the future of Indian Education System and its effects on the stakeholders*; *JMEIT*. October 2020, DOI:- 10.5281/ZENODO.4159546.
- Aithal Sreeramana and Aithal Shubhrajyotsna (2020) <https://mpr.ub.uni-muenchen.de/102549/> 26 Aug 2020 11:24 UTC. MPRA Paper No. 102549, posted Mridul Madhav Panditrao, Minnu Panditrao (2020) *National Education Policy 2020: What is in it for a student, a parent, a teacher, or us, as a Higher Education Institution/University?* <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/346819976>
- Pankaj Thakur and Dr. Rajesh Kumar (2021), *EDUCATIONAL POLICIES, COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF NATIONAL EDUCATION POLICIES OF INDIA AND CHALLENGES*. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Education Research*. ISSN:- 2277-7881; Peer reviewed and referred journal, Volume 10 Issue 3(5), March 2021.
- Dr. Hemlata Verma and Adarsh Kumar (2021):- *New Education Policy 2020 of India: A Theoretical Analysis* *International Journal of Business and Management Research (IJBMR)*, Review Article | Volume 9, Issue 3 | Pages 302-306 | e-ISSN: 2347-4696.
- Dr. Nandini Banarjee, Dr. Amarnath Das, Ms. Sreya Ghosh (2021) *NATIONAL EDUCATION POLICY (2020): A CRITICAL ANALYSIS*. *Towards Excellence*, UGC- Human Resource Development Center Gujrat University, Ahmedabad. ISSN NO. 0974 035X. 7. Shashidharan M, Rajni Bansal, B S Hothi, Vijay Anant Athavale, Yogesh Mahajan, Shameem Anwar,(2021) *A Review on National Education Policy 2020 and Its Influence on Academics*. *Research Article: 2021 Vol: 24 Issue: 1S*. DOI: 10.9790/7388-1302015661 www.iosrjournals.org 60 | Page “A Review on National Education Policy 2020.”
- Dr. P.K Jain (2021), *A critical analysis of new education policy 2020 and its future implications*. *Journal of commerce and trade/October 2021/Vol.XVI/No.2/RNI UPENG03027/P-ISSN 0973-4503/E-ISSN 2454-1702*. DOI :
- Shubhada MR Nirantha MR (2021) *International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews (IJRAR)*, May 2021, Volume 8, Issue 2. E-ISSN 2348-1269, P- ISSN 2349-5138, www.Ijrar.org .
- Dr. Praveen Kumar Sharma and Sanjeevan Bala (2022), *A study of national education policy 2020, awareness among secondary school teachers in district Kangra*. *International Journal of Advanced Academic studies* 2022; 4(1):240-244. E-ISSN: 2706-8927 P ISSN: 2706-8919. <http://www.allstudyjournal.com> .
- Dr. Ruchi Rani (2022) *Journal of research in humanities and social science*, Volume 10 –Issue 2(2022) PP: 06-09, ISSN (Online) 2321-9467.
- Gopalan K.R, Nivithra S., Vezhavendhan D. (2021) *Public Opinion on the new education policy 2020*. *Journal for Educators, Teachers and Trainers*, Vol. 13 (1), ISSN 1989 – 9572, DOI: 10.47750/jett.2022.13.01.021.

- Dr. Prativindhya Saini (2022) *Analysis of NEP 2020 in the Light of NAAC Accreditation: An Analytical Study of Academicians Opinion*, *International Journal for Research in Applied Science and Engineering Technology*. ISSN: 2321-9653
- Roshan Lal Sondhiya *A Study on the awareness on New Education Policy (2020) among the schoolteachers in Jabalpur Distict (2022)*. © February 2022 | *IJIRT* | Volume 8 Issue 9 | ISSN: 2349-6002.
- Dr. Deepa Choudhari (2022):- *A Study on National Education Policy – 2020 and its Impact on Stakeholders w.r.t Higher Education Institutions of Nagpur City*. *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews*, Vol 3, no 2, pp 390-394, February 2022 Journal homepage: www.ijrpr.com ISSN 2582-7421
- Abhimanyu Kumar (2022) *National Education Policy 2020 and preparedness of Ayurveda Universities*. © 2022 *International Journal of Ayurveda Research* | Published by Wolters Kluwer – Medknow
https://mpr.ub.uni-muenchen.de/102549/1/MPRA_paper_102549.pdf
[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/National_Policy_on_Education#:~:text=In%201986%20C%20the%20government%20led,Scheduled%20Caste%20\(SC\)%20communities.](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/National_Policy_on_Education#:~:text=In%201986%20C%20the%20government%20led,Scheduled%20Caste%20(SC)%20communities.)
http://epgp.inflibnet.ac.in/epgpdata/uploads/epgp_content/S000033SO/P000300/M013097/ET/145258955205ET.pdf
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sarva_Shiksha_Abhiyan